

Dynamic Storage Selection for Mitigating Tail Latency in Serverless Pipelines

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Abstract—In the rapidly evolving landscape of cloud computing, serverless computing has seen significant growth, offering a user-friendly programming interface for building scalable microservices at reduced costs. However, due to its stateless nature, managing intermediate results in complex application pipelines is challenging due to the need for distributed object storage like Azure Blob Storage, AWS S3, or Redis. To address this challenge, we propose HyperStore, an ephemeral storage management framework that features a smart function container enabling seamless and real-time interaction with various storage providers, without altering the function code. Furthermore, HyperStore dynamically determines and selects the optimal storage for each pipeline function to meet Service Level Objectives (SLOs) at minimal cost and mitigate tail latency. Our framework can be integrated with existing Serverless systems such as OpenFaas, allowing function containers to communicate via a shared host volume for reduced latency in case of function co-location. Our detailed experimental results demonstrate the efficiency and advantages of our approach.

Index Terms—storage selection, serverless, tail latency

I. INTRODUCTION

The emerging serverless computing model (AWS Lambda [1], AWS Fargate, Azure Functions [2], and Google Cloud Functions [3]) has received significant attention in recent years as it introduces a new way of building and developing applications, eliminating the need for manually provisioning and maintaining servers, allowing the developers to concentrate solely on coding the application logic without managing the underlying infrastructure. Furthermore, it provides high scalability and reduces operational costs through a pay-as-you-go pricing policy where users are charged only for the resources consumed during the execution of their workloads, making it suitable for various domains such as event stream processing, web services, ETL functions and video analytics.

Thus, many organizations choose the serverless computing model to structure and deploy their applications; these are typically expressed as pipelines of serverless functions packaged within containers or microVMs. Applications execute on demand, and they often need to share intermediate data across the functions of the pipeline. In contrast to traditional systems, direct inter-function communication is not always possible or is subject to payload size limitations. Thus, the de-facto way to implement inter-function data exchange is to use shared object storage or a shared Key-Value (KV) caching system across the functions of the pipeline. Functions write intermediate results to the object storage/KV system and the corresponding object IDs are propagated to the next function(s), which can access

the object via a remote call to the storage. These intermediate data are usually *ephemeral*, indicating that they are short-lived with a lifetime equal to the execution of the pipeline.

To meet the demands for scale and performance of the applications, cloud object stores are recently being utilized in concert with networked, in-memory object caches such as Redis and Memcached. Cloud providers offer their tenants a variety of storage options, or storage tiers, varying from modern and fast solid-state storage devices such as SSDs and NVMe drives to more traditional HDDs, which makes the choice of storage deployment flexible, but also non-trivial. In addition to typical storage services such as AWS S3, Microsoft Azure Blob Storage, Google Cloud Storage and Alibaba OSS, new providers are exploiting new object storage systems. These constitute fundamental components of cloud platforms and represent a robust and scalable solution for storing vast amounts of unstructured, and often diverse data, ranging from documents, images, and videos to binary objects and serialized objects. Each tier offers different features and has different cost and performance (*i.e.*, latency and throughput) tradeoffs. Furthermore, it is also common for cloud providers to offer different performance tiers of the same storage system. For example, Azure Blob Storage and AWS S3 offer a Standard Tier and a Premium Tier for non archival data. Premium tiers typically use faster SSD disks and offer consistently lower read/write latency compared to Standard, but it costs up to 10x more per GB than the Standard. To achieve even faster response times, in-memory storage systems such as Redis or Memcached can be used to provide the lowest read/write delays. Although in-memory systems like Redis typically charge by the hour for a predefined capacity, the corresponding cost is orders of magnitude higher per GB.

Selecting the most appropriate storage system for storing the ephemeral intermediate results that are generated during the execution of the pipeline is non trivial, given their time constraints and diverse latency requirements. Always choosing in-memory storage may be faster, yet it is the most expensive storage system, and although it can effectively meet latency demands, it may lead to increased costs, especially for tasks with long execution times. On the other side, opting for storage with lower costs may hinder the near real-time execution of the serverless pipelines, leading to reduced application responsiveness, increased tail-latency and ultimately missed deadlines. We find that a surprisingly large number of serverless workloads can benefit from increased performance by

Fig. 1: Latency benchmark for the different storage tiers in Microsoft Azure. (y-axis is in logarithmic scale)

just switching to a storage system that offers lower latency. This means that selecting the most appropriate storage system dynamically based on deadline constraints can allow us to meet latency constraints but at a reduced expense without having to upscale vertically the applications. For example, using premium storage for time-critical requests and selecting more economical alternatives for requests with longer deadlines ensures that applications achieve their performance objectives while upholding a cost-efficient storage approach adapted to the diverse demands of serverless workloads. Furthermore, apart from identifying the appropriate storage system, an extra burden that the developers have to deal with is adapting their function code to use the appropriate storage system APIs or SDKs. This is not always an easy task, and there are inherent complexities (difficult to adapt legacy code or programming language limitations).

A large body of research has focused on optimizing the efficiency of ephemeral storage systems. Pocket [4], InfiniCache [5] and InfiniStore [6] provide alternative storage systems that are designed specifically for serverless systems. These systems constitute substitutes for the object storage systems provided by the cloud providers. Monarch [7] on the other hand, is a middleware that transparently employs storage tiering to accelerate Deep Learning training. These works are limited as they either propose completely tailor-made storage systems or focus only on specific applications.

Motivating Example. We performed the following experiment to study the performance benefits and corresponding costs when serverless pipelines exploit the tiered storage in the cloud. We utilized various-sized blobs in the three aforementioned data storage types in Microsoft Azure where we measured the corresponding download/upload response times. Following recent studies [8] [6] which indicates that Serverless applications access objects of various sizes, ranging from some KBs to several MBs, we varied the size of objects that we used in our benchmarks from 10KB, 4MB and 16MB objects. We performed 100 subsequent write/read operations for each object size in each tier of Azure (Blob Storage Standard / Premium and Redis) and we calculated the latency distribution for each test. In Figure 1 we observe that depending on the object size, the performance of the storage systems varies; larger object sizes result in higher latencies. The figures clearly illustrate that Redis is consistently faster compared to the other two options. A final very important aspect is the formation of

tail-latency. Tail-latency refers to the maximum or worst-case latency observed in a system, often associated with the slowest responses or outliers in a distribution of response times. We observe that Azure Blob Storage in the Standard Tier and Redis in the tested setup are more prone to tail-latency than the Premium Tier of Azure Blob Storage. However, Redis achieves lower average latency under all circumstances. We observe that Redis achieves lower upload latency than download. This is due to the fact that during downloads, the object has to be written in the local file system of the containers, which is slower than reading it during uploads. Shahrads et al. in [9] found that 50% of the function invocations last less than 1s and 90% less than 3s. Therefore the latency associated with object accessing in the shared storage takes a significant amount of the total execution time of the invocation. Also in Figure 1 we can observe that the instability in the storage access times can lead to increased total execution time of the request and consequently increased tail-latency.

We also measured the corresponding costs as follows: using the Pricing Calculator [2] provided by Azure, the cost of storing 50GB of data during one month in the East US region is \$2.45 with Standard performance and Hot Tier while the cost is \$8.40 with Premium performance. Both tiers are billed on a daily basis. Also, we observe that *Azure Cache for Redis*, which is a commercially managed version of Redis, has an hourly rate of \$2.1 in Standard Tier for approximately 50GB of storage. By considering the above observations, we realise that by exploiting the different performance and pricing characteristics of the various available storage solutions, we can plan and orchestrate the execution of time-sensitive streaming serverless pipelines in such a way that the pipeline’s SLOs are met and also that the total execution cost is kept at its minimum without SLO violations and tail-latency. Smart city analytics systems, such as [10] and [11] can benefit from a dynamic selection of storage tiers as they process a variety of requests from object detection to bike rebalancing, with different priorities and varying SLO requirements.

In this paper, we present HyperStore, a framework that exploits heterogeneous storage systems for storing ephemeral intermediate results during the execution of serverless pipelines by automatically determining the storage tier based on real-time latency indicators. HyperStore can intercept the file related system calls originating from the function in real-time and can dynamically re-direct them to use different

storage tiers according to the function latency requirements. The function developer does not need to have any knowledge of the underlying storage systems and can access intermediate results (objects) with simple file system calls such as `open()`, `read()` etc. In this way, HyperStore can integrate with any serverless system that uses Docker Images for deploying functions such as OpenFaaS, Azure Functions and AWS Fargate. The developer has to only include the function code in the HyperStore container, similarly to the OpenFaaS function templates. HyperStore (i) provides a smart container that can adapt the function code to use any remote object storage without the need to use external APIs, (ii) automatically determines the most appropriate storage selection for each function in the pipeline to meet the SLOs set by the user at the lowest possible storage cost, (iii) delivers a pipeline orchestration tool, similar to AWS Step Functions, that can automatically invoke Function Pipelines with heterogeneous storage given an application graph. We provide detailed experimental results to illustrate the working and benefits of our approach.

II. APPLICATION MODEL

HyperStore is designed to support the execution of serverless streaming pipelines comprising a number of cloud functions. Similar to [12], each application is represented as a Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG) denoted as $G = (V, E)$. We call this *Dependency Flow DAG* where V represents the set of serverless functions that comprise the application, and each edge $(i, j) \in E$ shows the dependencies among functions i and j , i.e., function j receives input from function i . A function can be invoked only after all its parents complete execution.

A Pipeline refers to a series of serverless function calls usually activated by a Message or Request or an Event and it is represented by the Dependency Flow DAG. The instantiation of the functions are called PNodes. Every PNode is dedicated to the processing of a single function and has its unique ID. PNodes can be instantiated within virtual machines or containers and are capable of replication to meet varying workload requirements. The degree of replication depends on configuration settings as well as latency and throughput criteria. Typically, it is managed by the underlying serverless system. In our system, we assume that all the functions of the same Pipeline are hosted within the same data center. Each PNode manages a set of HTTP connections to the serverless function, one for each function replica. These connections are established through a Gateway provided by the Serverless system. The number of HTTP connections aligns with the number of function replicas available.

An execution dependency does not always represent the sequence of execution of the functions within the pipeline. For example, a dependency $(a \rightarrow b, a \rightarrow c)$ means that functions b and c both require intermediate results from function a , but it is not necessary that function c is called immediately after the execution of a . For these reasons, we denote the execution sequence with solid edges in the *Dependency Flow DAG*. One function has to fully complete its execution and generate its intermediate result in order to start the next function. For each

edge, we assign a weight, which indicates the size of the intermediate results that are exchanged between the functions, which leads to the associated storage latency.

We consider that all functions have access to the cluster's tiered storage that is utilized for writing, reading, and exchanging intermediate results. This tiered storage is provided by a cloud storage provider, such as Azure Blob Storage or Redis and the data are hosted in the same region as the functions. The intermediate results that are produced during the execution of a single request by the pipeline persist for the duration of the pipeline execution.

In the serverless computing model, there is no direct communication between the functions; these are invoked by an external orchestration tool like AWS Step Functions [13], or Apache Airflow [14] which is in charge of the corresponding invocations. Each function returns the keys of the objects containing its generated results. The return value can be formatted either as a single JSON Object or an Array Of JSON Objects. For a single JSON Object, a single request to the next function will be triggered, but for an Array of n JSON Objects, n parallel request will be invoked to the next functions.

In terms of flow control, we consider that the pipelines must be able to handle the following forms of communication: *Sequential*, where each request is propagated from function to function, *Split*, where the flow branches to sub-flows and a single request is propagated to two or more branches concurrently, *Parallel and Split-Parallel*, only for Arrays of intermediate results, where multiple intermediate results can be processed in parallel by different replicas of the same functions for increased throughput, and finally *Merge*, where two different branches of the same flow merge back to a single flow, or multiple requests that have been processed in parallel are merged for returning a single result.

III. ARCHITECTURE

A. Overall architecture

Pipeline Orchestrator: There have been developed several pipeline orchestrators, like AWS Step Functions, Apache Airflow and AMESoS [15], that can automatically orchestrate the sequence of execution of serverless functions expressed as a DAG. In our system, we designed a custom pipeline orchestrator similar to the ones above. The benefit of our orchestrator is that it can also handle the connection with different storage systems, by injecting into the function requests information about the location of the intermediate results. The Pipeline Orchestrator is one of the main components of HyperStore. It instantiates a set of PNodes as described in the pipeline configuration file, where the user describes the dependency flow DAG of the functions and the *latency_classes* of the pipeline. It is in charge of managing the execution of the pipeline and maintaining the corresponding metadata. As metadata, we consider any information about the intermediate result objects that is related to the storage selection. It executes the pipeline by continuously receiving flow invocations (requests) from the users or any other API and executing the set of invocations for each PNode of the pipeline. For each flow invocation, it

Fig. 2: Overall System architecture

instantiates a JSON object called DataFlow that contains the keys of the intermediate results. The DataFlow object also contains a meta-data section that includes information related to the location and storage tier of each intermediate result, as well as information about the storage tier that should be used for the next invocation. It can select in real-time the ephemeral storage to be used at each PNode for every invocation. This is done by exploiting the resource and performance information such as laxity and the *latency_class* of the request. In section IV-C we describe in detail our storage selection algorithm that computes in real-time the performance vs cost value for each invocation and can set the appropriate meta-data values in the request. In addition, it maintains statistics about the execution of the pipeline, such as laxity, latency, invocations per second, the number of active function replicas for each PNode etc.

With the appropriate APIs, it can be adapted to use with any commercial or open-source Serverless system. The Pipeline Orchestrator can be deployed as a separate serverless container alongside the pipeline functions. One important aspect to consider is that the Pipeline Orchestrator is agnostic to the scaling and scheduling policies of the Serverless System.

HyperStore Container: The HyperStore container is the component that enables us to seamlessly use different storage tiers in real-time. An abstract overview of the container components is shown in Figure 2. It has a sub-component called Watchdog, which implements an HTTP server that is used to receive function request calls. Each request carries the actual payload for the function code and the DataFlow object. The Watchdog propagates the DataFlow object to the Interception Layer and the function payload to the actual function code. It also waits for the response of the function code and returns the result as an HTTP response to the initial HTTP request. The HyperStore Container allows users to focus only on the development of their function code rather than adapting it to the various storage tiers. Without the HyperStore container, the users have to use specific SDKs or APIs to interact with the different storage tiers, and they also have to include the functionality of the storage selection in their function code.

IV. METHODOLOGY

The primary goal of our approach is to seamlessly combine heterogeneous storage resources for the storage of ephemeral intermediate results in serverless streaming pipelines. Our

objective is to meet the pipelines' deadline targets, reduce tail latency, and keep the storage cost as low as possible.

A. Interception Layer

One of the main goals of our approach is to provide an easy-to-use container that can host the function code and can handle heterogeneous storage tiers without any interaction or knowledge of the underlying technologies from the developers. For this reason, we need a mechanism to transparently intercept the system calls made by the function code related to file operations, such as `open()` and `close()`. We accomplish this with an Interception layer between the kernel and the user code. One way to intercept system calls without requiring privileged execution of the container, is to use `LD_PRELOAD` [16]. The `LD_PRELOAD` is a well-known technique in Linux that allows the user to influence the linkage of shared libraries and the resolution of functions at runtime. It is a useful tool that can be used to override, interpose, or replace functions in a shared library. To intercept the system calls specific for file handling we have to re-implement them in a shared library that we link it in runtime during the execution of the function code. With our research, we confirm that the `LD_PRELOAD` technique can be used within Docker Containers without privileged capabilities to intercept the related system calls both in our local cluster and in Azure Functions. The interception layer communicates with the HyperStore Core API. In the case that the platform does not support the `LD_PRELOAD`, HyperStore can also be utilized via the HyperStore Core API through its HTTP API. The HyperStore Core API interacts with various cloud storage tiers in parallel via their respective interfaces. Any access keys/secrets for the various storage tiers are managed by the underlying serverless provider like any other typical function. The DataFlow object provided with each function invocation includes an index that contains the storage location of the required objects and information about the storage tier to be used for storing the generated results.

When an object is accessed, the Intermediate layer intercepts the system call (e.g. `open()` or `open64()`) and firstly, tries to access that object in the container storage. If the object is not present, it subsequently checks the provided index and finds the object's actual location and the storage used. Afterwards, by using the appropriate API it fetches the object from the cloud storage to the local container storage as a new file and

returns its file descriptor. When a file is modified or created in the container storage, the Intermediate layer sets an attribute *dirty* to that file that indicates that the file is altered. When the function code invokes the *close()* system call for that file, the Intermediate layer again intercepts the system call and checks if the file contains the attribute *dirty* to check if the file is altered, and therefore it needs to be synchronized to the cloud storage. In this case, it writes the file to the storage that is provided in the DataFlow object. Notice, here, that we can set it to check for modified files only in a specified paths. The Interception layer is compatible with function code written in any programming language because it acts as an intermediate between the function code and the Kernel.

B. Estimating the laxity value

Given a user-defined deadline constraint specified for a request, the Pipeline Orchestrator dynamically assesses whether that request can meet its deadline target. Several works in the literature [15] have highlighted the benefits of monitoring the laxity value instead of the number of deadline misses. In our work, we employ a Laxity Scheduling scheme. The benefit is that it is a dynamic algorithm that can adjust the scheduling of a request at run-time based on queuing delays. The Laxity Scheduling algorithm works as follows: it assigns a priority (*i.e.*, laxity value) to each pipeline request according to its urgency. The laxity of a pipeline request r is computed as the difference between the deadline and the estimated remaining execution time of the request in the pipeline. More formally,

$$laxity_r = timeToDeadline_r - estimate_r \quad (1)$$

where $estimate_r$ is the estimated remaining execution time for the request r in the pipeline. The smaller the laxity value is, the higher the probability of a deadline miss. A negative laxity value indicates that the request will not be able to execute the pipeline on time. Laxity represents a metric of urgency for each request and is updated at runtime.

In HyperStore, the execution of pipelines is repetitive but aperiodic. The execution time of a request in the pipeline, $estimate_r$, can be estimated from historical data of the pipeline or, similar to [17], by using a small number of invocation runs during a profiling period at the initialization of the pipeline. A pipeline is represented as a DAG in which the nodes represent serverless functions, known as Pipeline Nodes (or PNodes), and the connections among nodes in the DAG denote the respective function invocations. The execution latency TL_i at each PNode i is computed as follows:

$$TL_i = ql_i + pr_i + sa_i \quad (2)$$

where ql_i is the queuing latency, pr_i is the processing latency and sa_i is the Storage Access Latency.

The Queuing Latency (ql_i) is the amount of time the request is waiting at $PNode_i$'s queue before being processed. This depends on multiple factors, including (i) the scheduling policy, (ii) the arrival pattern of the incoming requests, and (iii) the scaling and parallelism decisions for the PNode function replicas. If the function is in a *cold state*, *i.e.*, there are

no running replicas at the time the request arrives, ql_i also includes the cold start latency. Processing Latency (pr_i) is the amount of time the function code takes to process a single request r . Note, that, this time does *not* include any I/O to external storage systems. Finally, Storage Access latency (sa_i) denotes the amount of time it takes to access (download and upload) the objects of the intermediate results in the tiered storage, such as Azure Blob Storage, Redis, S3, etc. In our experiments, we demonstrate that sa_i latency can take up to 30% of the total latency for a request.

Given that the pipeline is represented as a DAG, a pipeline can comprise functions that span among multiple branches (paths); thus, the latency of the DAG depends on the latency of the branch with the longest execution latency [18].

Our strategy involves computing dynamically the laxity value for each request that arrives at a PNode. This laxity value serves as a trigger for our Storage Selection algorithm, guiding the selection of the appropriate remote storage for storing intermediate results within each PNode. During the instantiation of the pipeline by the user, a set of latency classes can be provided to the Pipeline Orchestrator with the description of the pipeline, for example, *critical*, *medium*, *low*. Each class represents a deadline target in ms for each request. Then, during the execution of the pipeline, each request can carry an attribute *latency_class* which indicates its deadline or urgency. As we explain in detail later on, we assign the appropriate storage for each Pipeline step according to the *latency_class* of the request. Furthermore, by observing the laxity of the request, we can dynamically switch the storage allocation to the fastest one to speed up the execution in the case of unexpected delays, which is indicated by a drop in the laxity value of the request. For example, in the car detection scenario, discussed in the Evaluation section, a function splits a video into smaller clips, and each clip is processed by another function for car detection, the storage selection can be adjusted dynamically based on the urgency of the request. For example, if delays occur, a drop in the laxity value will be detected, in which case the storage tier will change to the fastest one to speed up the processing and avoid a deadline miss. Using the index in the DataFlow object, the next functions can locate and read the intermediate results from the different storage tiers. HyperStore is implemented as a stand-alone component that can be integrated into existing cloud platforms. In the case that a Serverless Provider chooses to integrate HyperStore into their platform, an additional feature of the smart container can be used. In the case of function co-location in the same physical machine, two or more HyperStore containers can bind a shared volume and directly exchange intermediate results without the need for external storage systems.

C. Optimal Storage Selection

From the *Dependency Flow* DAG of a serverless application pipeline, we can extract the dependency graph, which represents the flow of data between the functions. For example, a function node can read the intermediate results of

its parent nodes and their ancestors. We define the Reading Set (rs_{F_i}) of function i as the set of functions that function F_i require the reading of their intermediate results. Although the intermediate results read from the Reading Set can be fetched from different storage tiers, *each function can upload intermediate results only to one storage tier* during the execution of a single request. For example, during the processing of a request r , F_i can use one of the following storage systems, *AzureBlobStorage (ABS) Standard Tier*, *ABS Premium Tier* or *Redis* for persisting its results.

Each storage system is associated with a different latency, thus we designate the following three parameters, upload latency, download latency and cost values, for each of the various Storage Systems st and for different data sizes s , denoted as $Storage_{st,s} = (upload_{st,s}, download_{st,s}, cost_{st,s})$. Subsequently, with each value set, our objective is to identify the combination of storage that not only meets the specified constraints but also has the lowest monetary cost. Our first priority is to achieve the request deadline and then to achieve the lowest possible cost.

Each pipeline is represented as a DAG, $G(V, E)$. $V(|V| = n)$ is a set of nodes representing the PNodes in the pipeline and $E \subset V \times V$ is a set of edges. Each edge $E_{i,j}$ represents the interaction between two PNodes (i,j).

The execution latency TL_i of a $PNode_i$ is associated with the edges originating from the node as the weight of the edge. The start node of the Graph G is denoted as "1" and "n" denotes the final node of the Graph. Let us denote $P(n)$ the set of all paths in G from node "1" to node "n".

The latency of the DAG depends on the longest path $lp \in P(n)$. The length of path lp is the minimum time required for completion of a single request in the pipeline [18]. Thus,

$$estimate_r = \sum TL_i \forall i \in lp \quad (3)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\text{minimize} \quad \sum_{i=0}^N \sum_{j=0}^{u_i} cost_{x_i, s_{i,j}} \\ &\text{subject to} \quad estimate_r \leq deadline \quad x_i \in \{0, \dots, st\} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

We need to note here that for each PNode i its storage access latency sa_i is calculated as follows:

$$sa_i = uploadLatency_i + \sum_{i=1}^{|rs_i|} latency(r_i) \quad (5)$$

Where $uploadLatency_i$ is the latency in ms for writing the intermediate results of the function i and $latency(r_i)$ is the latency for reading the intermediate results from the previous functions in the pipeline from their respective storages.

Finding the longest path of a graph G is an NP-Hard problem in general. However, in the special case of DAGs, it can be solved in linear time with a modification of Dijkstra's algorithm. Dijkstra's Algorithm is a well-known algorithm that is used to find the shortest path of a DAG. The longest path between two given vertices s and t in a weighted DAG G is the same as the shortest path in a graph $-G$ derived from G by changing every weight to its negation.

$$C = \begin{pmatrix} s_{1,1} & s_{1,2} & s_{1,3} & \dots & s_{1,m} \\ s_{2,1} & s_{2,2} & s_{2,3} & \dots & s_{2,m} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ s_{n,1} & s_{n,2} & s_{n,3} & \dots & s_{n,m} \end{pmatrix}$$

where $St = \{..\}$ is the set of available storage tiers and each $s_{i,j} \in St$.

Matrix C contains all the possible combinations of storage selections for writing the intermediate results for each PNode in the pipeline. Each column represents a PNode in the pipeline. For each combination $c_n \in C$, the modified Dijkstra algorithm is used to calculate the longest path in the pipeline DAG. Then, with (3) we estimate the total execution latency of the whole pipeline for this combination. Given that different functions in the same pipeline can use different storage tiers, we select the storage combination that results in the lowest monetary storage cost and has a latency value below a given threshold provided by the user. We can also calculate different allocations for multiple latency classes, and in the online phase, select in real-time the appropriate one based on the *latency_class* attribute of each request.

According to [9] over 98% of applications in Azure Functions consist of fewer than 15 functions. That limits the search space enough so that an exhaustive search of all possible combinations is feasible in under 30 seconds, as observed during our experimentation. Of course, 30sec is an unacceptable latency for real-time applications, so we perform an offline selection of the storage type for each writing set during the first submission of the pipeline. In the case that an application consists of more than 25 functions at which point an exhaustive search is infeasible, we can select a predefined strategy for each latency class provided, e.g. ALL-PREMIUM for requests with medium laxity or ALL-REDIS for time-critical requests. By performing an exhaustive search in the whole search space, we guarantee to provide the cheapest strategy that meets the required Service Level Objective (SLO). Other approaches, such as Simulated Annealing, are approximations, and rather than guaranteeing finding the optimal solution, they provide a solution that is the closest fit to the requirements.

D. Utilizing in-memory storage systems

In-memory storage systems such as Redis or Memcached provide the fastest access to the objects but are also the most expensive to use. They are typically billed hourly, proportional to the allocated memory. In our solution, we propose to run the Redis system within a container. As we observed during our experiments, instantiating Redis in dedicated containers is faster than instantiating Azure Cache for Redis, furthermore, container instances can provide sufficient network bandwidth and can be allocated and de-allocated faster than instantiating a Redis cache service. As soon as we detect that arriving messages require Redis to achieve their deadline targets, the Pipeline Orchestrator can allocate a Redis container for the minimal time that it is billed. Then all subsequent critical requests can use the Redis container. After the allocation period, if there are no more critical requests, it can de-allocate

the container. If critical requests continue to arrive, we extend the allocation period for an equal duration as previously. To keep the cost as low as possible, we select the cheapest container plan that provides enough bandwidth to achieve the latency targets of the pipeline. Typically, the cheapest containers do not provide plenty of memory. For this reason, we schedule only the critical requests to use the Redis tier, and we exploit the ephemeral nature of the data to evict them from the cache after the completion of the request that generated them. Also, by scheduling only critical requests to Redis, we keep the network bandwidth usage of the Redis container as low as possible to avoid unnecessary delays. Finally, as we show in our motivation experiments, Redis performance degrades with larger objects.

E. Analyzing the execution of a single request

Let's analyze in detail the execution of each request in the pipeline. Figure 2 shows a high-level abstraction of the overall architecture of HyperStore. In the first step, the user sends a request to the Pipeline Orchestrator with HTTP. The request contains an attribute that indicates the desired deadline for the request. In step (2), the Pipeline Orchestrator selects the storage that is used for each step in the pipeline and creates the DataFlow object. Then it invokes the first function of the pipeline with the DataFlow object (2a) and the request payload as arguments. In step (2b) the Watchdog that runs inside the HyperStore container of the first function informs the Interception layer with the DataFlow object and triggers the function code. All object-related operations that are generated by the function code are intercepted by the Interception Layer and routed to the appropriate storage tier (2c) based on the received DataFlow object. The corresponding storage tier client performs the actual I/O operation with the remote storage (2d) and mirrors the action to the local container storage. Then it returns the actual file descriptor to the function code. The result of the first function is returned to the Pipeline Orchestrator to be used as a payload for the next function in the pipeline (3). This process continues until all steps in the pipeline are complete.

V. IMPLEMENTATION

We implemented all the components of HyperStore that are explained in this paper. The Watchdog contains around 500 lines of code and is implemented in Java 17. For the Interception layer, we created a shared library in C to use with LD_PRELOAD. We also used Java Redis, S3/Minio and Azure Blob Storage clients for interacting with the corresponding storage providers both locally and in the cloud. Both the Watchdog and the Interception layer are packaged into the same Docker Container. For this work, we can support functions written in Java and Python, there are plans for extending the available languages in the future. The Storage Profiler is written in Python and consists of around 100 lines of code. The Pipeline Orchestrator is implemented in Java 17 with a total of around 1500 lines of code. We also implemented three different workloads of various storage demands for

testing and evaluating our approach. The first workload is a car detection pipeline that uses computer vision to detect cars in small 20-second videos generated from live cameras. The other two workloads are synthetic workloads that are designed to further highlight certain capabilities of our approach.

VI. EVALUATION

A. Experimental Setup

1) *Hardware*: We conducted our experiments both in our local small edge cluster comprising 5 nodes and with Microsoft Azure. Each node in the local cluster has an Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-7700 CPU @ 3.60GHz processor with 4 physical cores and 8 threads and 16GB of RAM and 2 SATA3 SSD drives. We also used two separate clusters as our storage clusters. The first cluster consists of 4 nodes, each having an Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-3770 CPU @ 3.40GHz and 16GB of RAM and 2 1TB HDD spinning at 7200RPM. The second cluster consists of 2 nodes, each having an Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-7820X CPU @ 3.60GHz and 64GB of RAM and 2 512GB SATA3 SSDs. Finally, we used a separate machine with an Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-12700 and 64GB of RAM as our Redis cache server. All nodes are interconnected with 1Gbps Ethernet network through a central switch. On Microsoft Azure we used a set of Standard DS3 v2 and F2s v2 virtual machines for hosting auxiliary services and the Redis Nodes. We used Azure Functions for deploying the function containers.

2) *Software*: All of the nodes in the edge cluster run on Ubuntu 20.04 LTS. We use Apache Mesos [19] 1.9 and Marathon 1.5 [20] as the container orchestrator to deploy function containers. With the current hardware, Mesos reports in total 40 CPUs and 80GB of RAM available. Also, we used Minio as our object storage in both of our storage edge clusters, and Redis v7.2.3 running inside a Docker container with predefined CPU affinity for increased performance and stability. On the Azure side, we used Ubuntu 20.04 LTS for the VMs, Redis v7.2.3 in a Docker container running in a F2s v2 VM instance and Azure Blob Storage for the storage tier.

B. Evaluation methodology

In order to provide a complete evaluation of our approach, we designed and conducted a set of experiments that illustrate its performance and benefits. In the experiments, we used both real applications and synthetic workloads. One workload represents a video analytics pipeline [21], which uses machine learning to detect cars in traffic control camera data, and the other two are synthetic micro-benchmarks, similar to the ones used on [4], in order to have full control of the storage requirements. For simulating as close as possible the public cloud in the edge cloud, we performed multiple sets of benchmarks to our storage cluster in order to fine tune the simulation parameters. We used the Minio cluster with the HDDs as the Standard Tier and the one with the SSDs as the Premium Tier. Through our benchmarks, we observed similar behaviour in terms of tail-latency with the Azure cloud. Of course, the latency values are different than the Azure, but they are analogous. Because of the 1Gbps network, we had to

Fig. 3: Latency distributions for the three different workloads and for different storage selection policies. (y-axis is on a logarithmic scale)

Fig. 4: CDF of request latency for the Synthetic workloads with different SLO latency targets

introduce a small additional artificial latency to our *Premium* Tier in order to have increased latency compared to Redis, accordingly to the Azure performance.

HyperStore is not a new, separate storage system, thus its performance is limited by the performance of the storage systems that is using for the different storage tiers. It uses open-source available APIs to interact with the storage systems. Its throughput and latency values for each storage system, depend only on the storage system and the implementation of the API. It is not our goal to provide new or better APIs, nor do we try to increase the throughput of the storage tiers. The main evaluation is to illustrate: (i) the ability of a HyperStore Container to interact in real-time with multiple storage tier, (ii) the ability of the Storage Selector Component to select different storage tiers based on the required latency target of the pipeline, (iii) the negligible overhead of the HyperStore container and the performance of the offline storage profiling step and (iv) the cost benefit compared to baseline.

C. Evaluation Results

HyperStore is able to allocate the same storage tier for the entire pipeline or select a different tier at each step. In Fig. 3 we observe the total latency distribution of 100 sequential requests for the three workloads with different storage allocations, as well as the execution time. For the first two workloads, Synthetic Fig.3a and Synthetic#2 Fig.3b we observe that according to the desired storage selection policy, we can serve 4 different latency classes of requests. For Synthetic we serve requests with deadlines varying from 2.2s up to 6s. Similarly for Synthetic#2 we serve requests with deadlines from 1.5s up to 4.1s and for Car Detection Fig. 3c from 2.5s to 4s. For the first two workloads, HyperStore can create a mixed storage allocation for the different steps within the pipeline. As a result, it can achieve latencies between the

SSD and HDD policies. One important aspect to be considered is the tail-latency introduced by the different storage tiers. As we have also discussed in our motivation, Standard tiers can introduce extra latencies. In Fig. 3 we observe that the HDD tier consistently introduces tail-latency. As a result, SLOs like 99% might not be achievable, due to the large deviation. For example, in Figure 3b for a selected SLO '99% $\leq 3800ms$ ', the HDD tier is not fulfilled. On the other hand, HyperStore can target the SSD tier for some functions with the heaviest I/O to set the 99th percentile latency to under 3800ms. For the Car Detection workload, HyperStore was not able to create extra latency classes, due to the small size of the pipeline and the small size of the intermediate results of the 2 of 3 functions. The only possible speed-up is achieved by switching the storage tier of the first function, which extracts frames from the video clip. As a result, the newly generated latency class overlaps with the SSD latency. To demonstrate the functionality of HyperStore under different conditions, for each pipeline, we simulate both loose and tight deadlines to show how HyperStore behaves with requests with different SLO demands. However, the problem of identifying the optimal SLO target is an open problem [22], [23], [24]. In our approach, the selection of the SLO is tunable and can be chosen based on the characteristics of the pipeline. In Figures [4a,4b,4c] we observe the CDFs for three different scenarios for the Synthetic Workloads with different SLO targets. We observe that HyperStore achieved the target SLOs in all scenarios by generating mixed tier storage allocations.

To demonstrate HyperStore's real-time capabilities, we took a 5.5min snapshot of the Synthetic pipeline execution. The Pipeline is replicated with 4 function replicas at each step. In Figure 5 we observe the total I/O per second for each of the three different storage tiers. We use a mixed allocation of SSD

and HDD for non-critical latency classes and an ALL-REDIS strategy for critical requests. The requests arrive randomly following a normal distribution and a mean rate of 5 req/s. The rate is low enough and the system is operating without queuing. At times $t_1=100s$ and $t_2=290s$ we injected a random amount of critical requests. We observe that the IOPS of Redis increases, indicating that critical requests use Redis to be able to achieve their respective deadlines.

HyperStore can handle any object size without introducing significant latency overheads. In our machines we measured an average overhead for the interception layer of 2ms with maximum of 4ms. Also, it does not affect the function cold start latency. The object download/upload performance depends on three factors: (i) the technology of the storage system; (ii) the available bandwidth between the HyperStore function containers and the storage system; and (iii) the storage system provided APIs. In Figures 8 we observe the performance of HyperStore with various object sizes on Microsoft Azure Blob Storage. We designed a function that reads a specified object from a Blob Storage Container or Redis and writes it back. We deployed it with Azure Functions and we deployed a Redis instance inside an F2s v2 virtual machine. From Figure 7 we can observe that the performance and the tail latency, expressed as the 99th percentile, *depends on the underlying storage system* and not on the HyperStore container.

In terms of scalability, as Figure 8 shows, HyperStore can seamlessly scale horizontally. Again, the limiting factor is the available bandwidth between the HyperStore containers and the underlying storage systems. We used the same Azure Function, and we configured it to read 7MB and write a 4MB object from the different storage tiers. We measured the latencies for 50 requests. Each function replica can handle only one concurrent request. Then we replicated the function up to six instances, with different deployments for overriding the Azure queues. We observe that with the Azure Blob Storage tiers the latency remains around the same with all the replica configurations, while, we can clearly see that the limited bandwidth of the virtual machine that hosts the Redis instance affects the performance as more replicas concurrently use the Redis instance. When we increase the bandwidth of Redis VM to full 5 Gbps we see a vast improvement in the latency when the replication factor of the HyperStore containers increases.

Fig. 5: IOPS for each storage tier over a 5 min sample

Fig. 6: Redis Vs Co-location performance

Finally, we measured the benefit of Co-locating the pipeline functions at the same physical node. This is a special case and should be allowed by the underlying Serverless System. In

Fig. 6 we observe that by co-locating the pipeline of the Synthetic workload we can achieve around 1s better performance compared to using an ALL-REDIS strategy. In terms of cost, because HyperStore utilizes expensive Storage Tiers only for requests with strict SLOs it can reduce the average monthly storage cost in contrast to non-dynamic storage selection, where all messages have to be stored in the expensive tier.

VII. RELATED WORK

Pocket [4] is an elastic, distributed Ephemeral Storage designed to fulfil the performance needs of applications while maintaining cost-effectiveness. Pocket dynamically rightsizes resources and leverages multiple storage technologies to minimize cost while ensuring applications are not bottlenecked on I/O. InfiniCache [5] and InfiniStore [6] are distributed in-memory object caches that are built atop ephemeral cloud functions running on AWS Lambda. They use multiple Lambda functions, with each one being responsible for storing a portion of the entire data pool. Although HyperStore shares many common ideas with the previous works, HyperStore is not a new separate storage system. HyperStore acts more like a transparent bridge or middleware between different storage tiers that aims to effectively combine different storage systems inside serverless pipelines to achieve the lowest possible cost without violating the pipeline SLOs. Monarch [7] is a framework-agnostic storage tiering middleware for deep learning training. It accelerates Deep Learning training by mediating dataset read requests between different storage resources (local storage, shared parallel file system) while providing a data placement strategy that is fine-tuned for the I/O patterns of DL training workloads. Monarch enables DL frameworks to transparently leverage local storage devices of compute nodes, even for datasets that may not fit entirely on such resources. In contrast with HyperStore which is workload-agnostic, Monarch is oriented only for ML-based workloads. Pheromone [25] follows a data-centric approach and offers a set of data trigger primitives to control the flow of the intermediate results across the functions. On the other hand, Unum [26] provides function orchestration by utilizing intermediate representation that partitions higher-level application definitions at compile-time and runs as a runtime library that executes in parallel with user-defined serverless functions. OFC [27], is a transparent, vertically and horizontally elastic in-memory caching system for FaaS platforms, that opportunistically leverages overbooked host memory of serverless functions to accelerate function execution. FaaS\$T\$ [8] is a distributed cache that is co-located with FaaS functions on the same machines and offers high elasticity.

VIII. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we presented HyperStore, a framework designed to transparently use heterogeneous storage resources for storing ephemeral intermediate results of serverless Pipelines in order to mitigate the tail-latency of the pipeline, achieve the application SLOs and finally, reduce the operational cost to the lowest possible without violating the desired SLOs.

Fig. 7: Latency vs Object size with different storage tiers

Fig. 8: Scalability of each storage tier

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

We thank our shepherd, Prof. Christopher Stewart, and the anonymous ACSOS reviewers for their helpful feedback. The research work was supported by the Hellenic Foundation for Research and Innovation (HFRI) under the 3rd Call for HFRI PhD Fellowships (Fellowship Number: 6812), by the European Union through the EU ICT-48 2020 project TAILOR (No. 952215), the Horizon Europe AutoFair project (No. 101070568) and the Horizon Europe CoDiet project (No. 101084642).

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